

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FITSUM TEKESTE****FIRST NAME: NATNAEL****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

THE ART OF ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Essay writing is an art that needs to be mastered in order to achieve academic and professional excellence. The ACA-401 course pack gives as a glimpse as to what amounts to a successful essay writing and the rules that guide the art. In this response paper, I shall attempt to summarize the crucial points of essay writing as I learned them from the ACA-401 course pack.

2) THE BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

Academic essay writing starts with a purpose. A purpose of persuading your reader of an idea that is based on evidence (EUCLID 2015, 2). In order to do that, the essay must have a clear answer as to the question I am raising in the paper and an argument to justify my statement. The point that I am trying to make must be discussed based on reasoning and evidence that I have to justify it. Since knowledge is always learned or experienced, all the evidences or information that I may have to justify my argument must be properly cited.

A writer has to understand the question he has to answer very well. Before embarking on the process of writing, the writer should write down everything he knows about the topic (EUCLID 2015, 3). Before I start writing an essay, I must first take some time to think, read and research the subject matter I am thinking of writing. So, it is important to start my work early and avoid procrastination.

In the beginning the essay should be in a draft form which eventually will be edited and refined to give it its final structure and substance (EUCLID 2015, 4). Then

step by step I must first clearly state the essay question and analyze it in order to understand exactly what the question requires and to identify what approach I must take to answer it.

Then I must develop a thesis statement and argument to answer the essay question. In order to do that, I must do research in order to acquire the knowledge and evidence to allow me to develop the thesis statement and argument. Jotting down notes could help me keep record of my reading and can help me to locate information during my research.

After that I must organize my ideas considering the possible answer to the essay question, checking my notes for good examples and evidences supporting my answer, deciding on what points to discuss in detail and writing it down in an order I want to discuss on.

Then finally, in order to organize my initial thoughts and ideas to guide my research, I must write an essay plan. The essay plan will help me answer the essay question and what information to use and in what way to use it.

3) PLAGIARISM: UNETHICAL INTELLECTUAL THEFT

When writing papers one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism. Using sources of information of other authors without properly citing their work amounts to plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 8).

If I plagiarize the works of another and if I am caught it will bring me embarrassment or loss of reputation or even can make me out of job because it is seen as a form of intellectual theft. While writing any academic papers, it is natural to refer to some sources of other writers. However, I should not leave their work uncited because not citing the works of another might imply the idea is mine and that is wrong and unethical.

The ideas and people that you refer to need to be made explicit by a system of referencing: if you use another person's ideas or words, you must say where you have taken them from; if you do not, you risk being accused of plagiarism (Gillet, Hammond, and Martala 2009).

4) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

This unit allowed me to understand the *dos-and-don'ts* of writing successful papers. In a summary here is what I learned from this topic.

- Stating the main thesis at the beginning of the paper
- Critically assessing some important aspect of the thesis

- Not including generalities and writing clearly
- Taking the views, I am discussing seriously and supporting my assertions
- Avoiding plagiarism: if the paper is premised on the anti-thesis of another writer, the writer should objectively discuss his proposition and that of the original writer. (EUCLID 2015, 44)

5) LIT-101 REVIEW

This section clarified for me the use of comas, conjunctions, semicolons and other grammatical mistakes. It also introduced me to the two styles of writing, namely the UK and the US style guides. I also became aware of the Chicago or Turabian rules when and how to use them.

6) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Pronunciation, grammar, syntax and some spelling differences exist in the use of English language. In this section I managed to learn what amounts to American or British English and what the basic differences are. I also learned that, the US English is currently the most preferred language variety in the publication of different writings (EUCLID 2015, 54).

7) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

The ‘sample corrections to papers’ section was a very interesting read for me. Not only did I enjoyed reading the articles, I learned a lot from the corrections made to the text. The corrections certainly make the articles very interesting for the reader. I also learned that an article, although it may seem to be grammatically correct, the word structure may not always be as much.

8) ABEL SCRIBE’S CMS CRIB SHEET

This article highlighted the use of abbreviations, acronyms, capitalization, compound words etc. in the Chicago style of writing. It also described the Chicago way of page formatting and use of endnotes and footnotes. It also listed the abbreviations and expressions commonly used in writing.

9) CONCLUSION

During my previous academic career, I have written a number of essays, term and thesis papers. Reading the ACA-401 course pack I managed to identify a lot of mistakes that I was making over the years while writing them. I will use this course pack as a reference for my future academic endeavor.

REFERENCES

Gillet, Andy, Angela Hammond, and Mary Martala. 2009. *Successful Academic Writing*. First edition. Essex: Pearson.

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.